

Preparation of Triheteropoly Oxotungstomolybdodiarsenate(v)

S. K. ROY* and P. K. SINHA

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-834 008

Manuscript received 21 October 1997, revised 19 March 1998, accepted 20 March 1998

Sodium, guanidinium, tetramethylammonium and rubidium salts of triheteropolyoxoanion $[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}]^{6-}$ have been synthesized and characterized by chemical, thermal, infrared, electronic spectra and preliminary X-ray diffraction methods.

The literature reports heteropolypotassium 18-tungstodiarsenate^{1,2}. A number of triheteropoly salts of the type $M_x[X_2ZW_{17}O_{62}H_2].nH_2O$, where $M = K, C(NH_2)_3, (CH_3)_2NH_2$; $X = As$; $Z = Mn^{II}, Mn^{III}, Co^{II}, Co^{III}$ and Ni^{II} have also been reported^{3,4}. We report here the preparation of a few inorganic and organic salts containing 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate as a macro anion.

Results and Discussion

The solution of sodium salt of $[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}]^{6-}$ were examined spectrophotometrically in wide range of buffer solutions⁵. The compound appeared to be most stable at pH 2.86. The intense absorption bands at approximately $3.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 5.15 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is ascribed to charge transfer from oxygen to tungsten which is a characteristic for some polytungstate anions^{3,5}. The ir bands at $930-740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to the independent W-O stretching vibrations⁵. Broad bands at $820-780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to W-O-W bridge vibrations^{6,7}. Bands at $460-440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to tetrahedral AsO_4 linkage^{8,9}. Absorption at $1095-940 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to Mo-O stretching mode⁹. Various mixed bands at $3450-3370, 1660-1620$ and $640-590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are for water of crystallization, i.e. symmetric and asymmetric stretching of OH of lattice water, bending mode of lattice water and librational mode of constitutional water respectively^{6,8}. Absorption at 1390 cm^{-1} , found in organic salts, are due to N-H bonds.

$Na_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].28H_2O$: This compound is orthorhombic, $a = 16.89 \text{ \AA}, b = 18.65 \text{ \AA}, c = 14.82 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; $V = 4668.28 \text{ \AA}^3$ $Z = 2$; $\rho_{\text{calc}} = 3.559 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$, $\rho_{\text{expt}} = 3.602 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$; $M_{\text{obs}} = 5064.8$, $M_{\text{calc}} = 5005.17$.

$Rb_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].16H_2O$: Orthorhombic system, $a = 16.96 \text{ \AA}, b = 18.02 \text{ \AA}, c = 15.87 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; $V = 4850.177 \text{ \AA}^3$; $Z = 2$; space group $D_{2n}^2 - P_{\text{nnn}}$; $\rho_{\text{calc}} = 3.535 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$, $\rho_{\text{expt}} = 3.506 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$; $M_{\text{obs}} = 5121.9$, $M_{\text{calc}} = 5164.05$.

The analysis of X-ray powder file¹⁰ of $[C(NH_2)_3]_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].9H_2O$ revealed that the maximum relative intensities III_{c} is 32 with respect to the interplanar distance 13.1 \AA . The 100 point III_{c} corresponds to the d value

of 10.3 \AA . The density of the compound was found to be 3.416 g ml^{-1} by picnometric measurement.

The thermoderivatographic analysis¹¹ of the compounds were carried out. All the compounds lose water of crystallization reflecting some endotherms. First large endothermic peak appeared below 423 K denoting loss of water of crystallization which was confirmed by loss in weight. Some endotherms appeared at $473-523 \pm 10 \text{ K}$ indicating further loss of water of crystallization at different temperatures. In the temperature range $523-773 \text{ K}$, neither peak in the thermograms nor loss in weight were observed in cases of sodium and rubidium salts. Sharp exothermic peaks with change in physical state and colour followed by loss in weight corresponding to total loss of water of crystallization and decomposition of the anionic cage along with conversion of the compounds into respective metal oxides were observed above $573 \pm 20 \text{ K}$ in cases of guanidinium and tetramethylammonium salt, and above $773 \pm 20 \text{ K}$ in cases of sodium and rubidium salts which was confirmed by insolubility of the residual mass in water. The ir spectra of the ignited sample at this stage showed expected absence of bands for water molecules.

Experimental

Sodium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate(v): Stoichiometric quantities of As : Mo : W in ratio 2 : 1 : 17 were taken. Freshly prepared¹² and analyzed arsenic acid $H_3AsO_4.1/2H_2O$ (2.495 g, 16.532 mmol) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to lukewarm solution (125 ml) of sodium tungstate $Na_2WO_4.2H_2O$ (46.35 g, 140.52 mmol) with constant stirring. The mixture was allowed to cool. To it cold aqueous solution (25 ml) containing sodium molybdate $Na_2MoO_4.2H_2O$ (2 g, 8.266 mmol) was added slowly maintaining the pH at 2.86 using glycine-glycinehydrochloride buffer (pH range 1.0-3.7). The mixture was then refluxed using air condenser for 3 h. The resulting solution was then evaporated to one-fourth of original volume on a water-bath and left for crystallization at 278 K . The resulting dark yellowish red crystals were washed with alcohol and analyzed (Found : Na, 2.85; As, 3.20; Mo, 2.06; W, 61.8; O, 29.05; H, 1.04%). Molecular

formula of the compound was assigned on the basis of well established heteropoly anion $[X^{n+}]_2W_{18}O_{62}]^{(16-2n)-}$ as suggested by Dawson¹ ($Na_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].23H_2O$ calcd. for : Na, 2.76; As, 2.99; Mo, 1.92; W, 62.44; O, 28.77; H, 1.12%).

Guanidinium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsente(v) : It was prepared by metathesis from the sodium salt. A solution of sodium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate(v) (8.725 g, 1.745 mmol) in hot water (100 ml) was treated with guanidine hydrochloride (1 g, 10.47 mmol) in water (10 ml). The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 1 h and left overnight. Light orange coloured crystals obtained were air-dried and analyzed (Found : C, 1.5; N, 5.0; H, 1.21; As, 3.0; Mo, 2.0; W, 63.14; O, 24.15. $[C(NH_2)_3]_6-[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].9H_2O$ calcd. for : C, 1.48; N, 5.16; H, 1.10; As, 3.07; Mo, 1.96; W, 63.98; O, 23.25%).

Tetramethylammonium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate(v) : The tetramethylammonium salt of the mixed heteropolyanion $[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}]^{6-}$ was prepared by reacting aqueous solution (100 ml) of sodium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsente(v) (7.623 g, 1.523 mmol) with aqueous solution (10 ml) containing tetramethylammonium chloride (1.0 g, 9.136 mmol) by a method analogous to that described above for the guanidinium salt. The resulting creamish yellow powder was air-dried and analyzed (Found : N, 1.70; C, 5.69; H, 1.90; As, 3.0; Mo, 1.9; W, 62.0; O, 23.81. $[N(CH_3)_4]_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].12H_2O$ calcd. for : N, 1.67; C, 5.73; H, 1.91; As, 2.98; Mo, 1.91; W, 62.22; O, 23.58%).

Rubidium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate(v) : Rubidium salt with 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate as anion, was prepared by metathesis process from sodium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate, taking the stoichiometric quantity of Rb ion with Na ion. An aqueous solution (100 ml) containing sodium 17-tungstomolybdodiarsenate (7.222 g, 1.443 mmol) was treated with rubidium carbonate (2 g, 8.60 mmol) dissolved in water (25 ml) by a method analogous to that used for preparation of guanidinium and tetramethylammonium salts as described above. The resulting pale yellow crystals were dried and recrystallized from ethanol and analyzed (Found : Rb, 10.04; As, 3.0; Mo, 1.9; W, 60.01; H, 0.59; O, 24.46. $Rb_6[As_2MoW_{17}O_{62}].$

$16H_2O$ calcd. for : Rb, 9.93; As, 2.90; Mo, 1.86; W, 60.52; O, 24.17; H, 0.62%).

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The elemental analyses of the compounds were carried out using standard methods. Tungsten¹³ was estimated as WO_3 , molybdenum¹⁴ as MoO_3 and arsenic¹⁴ as magnesium ammonium arsente. Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometry. Thermoderivatographic analyses were carried out on a STA 409 (Netzsch) analyzer. X-Ray diffraction was recorded on a D 500/501 (Siemens) instrument. Preliminary X-ray¹⁵ data of the crystalline samples were recorded with CuK_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 1.5412 \text{ \AA}$). The densities were determined by floatation method in $CCl_4-C_2H_2Br_4$ at room temperature (298 K). Ir spectra¹⁶ were recorded on Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer.

References

1. B. DAWSON, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1953, 6, 113.
2. M. KERKER, D. LEE and A. CHOU, *J Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1539.
3. S. A. MALIK and T. J. R. WEAKLEY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2647.
4. S. K. ROY and K. C. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 68, 462.
5. S. K. ROY, R. JAISWAL and K. C. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, 31, 64.
6. T. J. R. WEAKLEY, *Struct. Bonding*, 1974, 18, 153.
7. G. A. TSIGDINOS, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1978, 76, 54.
8. M. T. POPE, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometallates", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1983.
9. D. H. BROWN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, 19, 583.
10. "X-ray Powder File", A. S. T. M. Inorganic Sets, 1-10.
11. R. C. MACKENJIE, "Differential Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1970, Vol. 1.
12. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1972.
13. W. W. SCOTT and N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Technical Press, London, 1958, Vol. I.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1961 and 1965.
15. N. F. N. HERY, M. LIPSON and W. A. WOSTER, "The Interpretation of X-ray Photographs", McMillan, London, 1960.
16. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.